

A Study of Users' Cognitive Load in eCommerce Websites using Eye-tracking Technology

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Abstract—Online shopping has evolved over the years, but the recent COVID-19 pandemic makes it faster than ever. People prefer online shopping rather than physical shopping to avoid the crowd because it is convenient, time-saving and hassle-free. Therefore, we have experimented to find a correlation between the cognitive load and product of e-commerce websites which play a vital role in influencing the buyers' decisions and purchasing habits. This research empirically inspects the cognitive load by leveraging observation and analysis of users' datasets. We have conducted the eye-tracking study sessions in lab conditions where volunteers were asked to buy products on a limited budget and within a specific time frame. After that, we have observed the eye movements of calibration using third party software called gazerecorder, which gives us the necessary data to work on further procedures. We verified those observed data with survey form analysis to ensure the authenticity of the experiment. In the meantime, we used eye-tracking methodologies and statistic calculation to reach the study result. Also, our result suggests how cognitive loads affect users' visual attention and behaviour towards different web interfaces. The findings illustrate how products prices affect users' visual attention and behaviour while viewing enlisted products. Moreover, eye-tracking calibration of users' eye movement indicates that the total fixation and task completion time were highest on the low-classified website when users buy a product. In contrast, another standardisation method, saccades, were not substantially different on the medium-classified website but were longer than others by duration. These findings will support the website product managers and developers to improve users' shopping experience. This study will provide guidelines for them to employ new information that would be considered while exhibiting products on the eCommerce websites. As a result, consumers can select the desired product by mitigating task completion time with the innate use of STM (short time memory).

Index Terms—cognitive load, eye-tracking, e-comm, hci, Website complexity

I. INTRODUCTION

In many affluent and developing countries, e-commerce continues to increase year after year. It is expected that by the year 2023, the market dominance of e-commerce platforms in Bangladesh will rise to 3 billion from 1 billion [1]. Although the global economy suffered during the COVID-19 situation, the traditional market moved rapidly over online to sustain itself in the business. Besides, strict quarantine forces consumers to become more internet centred in the post-pandemic position. Moreover, the transparency and flexibility of e-commerce platforms make them more appealing to the vast majority. We believe all websites need to be functioning in such a way too complacent to the users and ensure that the UCD (User-centric design) and HCD (Human-Centred Design) principles have been applied. To enhance the website's efficiency, we studied the cognitive load by taking into account users' visual perception. We categorized the websites and researched specific product pages, which is particularly significant because it discloses an initial interaction with users before buying a product. This initial feeling is part and parcel of triggering users' assumptions and may impact whether they purchase from the site. If consumers experience too many complexities while surfing product displaying pages, it might adversely affect their mental model of products and purchasing behaviour [2]. From the web developers' perspective, it is a foremost concern to ensure users' attention [2], [3], using the

website with ease and providing a greater experience so that they do not hesitate to visit that website again [2].

Visual perception means what the brain feels after observing the surroundings, and cognitive response means what the brain understands and reacts to. As many varieties of people live worldwide, every person may have their unique perception, perspective, and views. Therefore, someone may like particular aesthetics and maybe be disliked by someone else. Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) of low visual complexity tend to have higher aesthetics, usability, and accessibility and leave higher user satisfaction [4]. Furthermore, this aesthetics has a relationship with webpage complexity which contains GUIs. It is also suggested that the consumers respond to the web pages that fall in a moderate range of perceived complexity [3]. The relationship between webpage complexity and aesthetics is discussed by Substantial Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) research but without a decisive ending. The issue of investigating cognitive load is one of the most difficult aspects of HCI. An opposite linear correlation is shown by some research, whereas some other research shows an inverse linear correlation, even the rest showed no relationship at all [5]. As a result, hypothesis formulation is complicated by a lack of clarity. So, It is already seen that other research has different findings based on their methods and parameters and to generalise a model or make a uniform model that will be accurate and acceptable for all varieties of people all around the world considering their perception, perspective, and views are not accessible.

Another critical factor is the product's price which plays an essential role in buyers choosing a product through surfing web pages. Apart from consumers' perception, prices can be used to determine both the amount of effort required to choose a product and the level of quality [6]. The use of price as an indicator of product quality, according to Scitovszky (1945), is not irrational but rather expresses a conviction that pricing in the marketplace is decided by the interaction of competitive supply and demand factors. Such dynamics would result in a "natural" ordering on a price scale of competing products, resulting in a solid actual positive link between price and product quality. Given that price and quality are positively associated, customers are likely to utilise price as a quality indicator [7]. This study is also briefly devoted to figuring out the trigger of prices and how it influences a customer's purchasing habits.

A. Statement of Problem

An e-commerce site's business relies on its website, where the website design determines how well it will enable users to purchase and sell tangible products, services, and digital goods through the internet. Lots of exertion need to comprehend visual perception and the underlying psychology behind "making a site look good" because acquiring it right from a visual angle is elemental. The complexity of the website defines the quality of its user interface or the mental impact on users' cognition, and it all works together. To understand the visual perception of the website's effectiveness or improve it, finding

relations of website visual perception considering the cognitive load. If the user experience is not good enough to convince a user for taking further interaction, then the website's purposes will malfunction. Most of the time, the orthodox way of developing a site is not enough to resolve the issue. Here, we have worked with two methods to discover underlying reasons for users' cognitive measurements, Fixations and Saccades. We tried to find out the users visually focus on relevant parts when performing a task by using these mechanisms. It would help us to distinguish user cognitive effort and website complexity.

B. Objective of Study

The main goal of our study is to find the relation between e-commerce product price and cognitive load. The study will discover the cognitive load effects of users while using e-commerce websites.

C. Hypothesis

One of the main reasons for this study is to find the complexity of the cognitive response of website visitors. We believe e-commerce websites means the typical task of purchasing a product from an online retailer that can illustrate the complexity of online activities. Traditional websites with high complexity give plenty of information signals that need a great deal of attention and time to observe and interpret [8]. However, the entire retailer and wholesale industries rely on a single website that has to be designed faultlessly to find the desired product they intend to buy. Moreover, the perception of users and their cognitive load are intrinsically related so that the interaction between websites and humans happens immensely fast. Browsing interactions occur mostly in the subconscious part of our brain [12], which result in speedy actions. If the cognitive load of e-commerce platforms are high, it is needless to say that the interactivity will be laggard, and consumer satisfaction and loyalty will be lost [11]. Also, a complex website will divert customers' attention and create more fixations [13]. From our homework about CLT (Cognitive Load Theory) [14], which is rarely taken into account in e-commerce studies, we were motivated enough to investigate e-commerce sites to find out variables and reasons for the varying cognitive load. Besides, many variables could increase the complexity of a website. As a result, the primary goal of this study is to evaluate the accompanying below hypothesis, which will formulate outcomes based on our experiment, statistical analysis and cumulative assessment.

- H1.** The lower the website products' price from the budget range, the higher the user's number of fixation.
- H2.** The lower the website products' price from the budget range, the longer the user's task compilation time.
- H3.** The closer the website products' price from the budget range, the longer the user's saccades.
- H4.** The lower the website products' price from the budget range, the longer the user's fixation duration.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Background of the Study

Website visual perception has been an active area of research for a long time. Numerous tools and associate architects models have been developed and proposed for creating the adaptive UI. Every day, technologies evolve, and the interaction between humans and machines becomes more ubiquitous in our daily lives. Every advancement in the technology sector brings new challenges in our everyday lives. Latest gadgets and applications allow immense possibilities and interactions between man and machine. HCD comes into practice to ensure this interactivity fluently. HCD is the set of procedures to build a bridge between the people's capabilities and needs that fit appropriately with the system. Moreover, HCD stated that a subtle design begins with the utilisation of modern technologies and an understanding of human psychology [12]. It offers some vital principles prioritising human perception and focus compatibility of design by setting up a suitable approach.

In our study, experiments are based on this core design philosophy. We have tried to find materials that caused impedance and made users woeful about their website browsing experience. We understand it is challenging to produce human-centric design, especially e-commerce websites and organise products in such a way that the consumer would surely revisit later. Furthermore, research on the nature of design characteristics and how to employ them have produced conceptual approaches and statistical findings. This section briefly explores those proposed reference architectures, models, adaptation techniques, and available tools, along with their limitations.

B. Related Work

Alexandre et al. [2] considerate that presents visual complexity as having an impact on valence and arousal judgments. They examined 36 sample website homepages to investigate the visual complexity for determining users' perception of psychological responses. Nevertheless, there is no clarity on what factors in website design cause visual complexity and how complexity is similar to several aspects of HCI, such as usability.

Geissler et al. [3] examined the user's attention to the home page, attitude toward the home page, and purchase intent to measure the impact of home page complexity. They conducted two types of experiments, qualitative and pretest. In the qualitative process, they surveyed 30 web designers (both male and female) over a phone call to get an observation about web pages. On the other hand, 169 undergraduate students were the test subject for the pretest process in website evaluation. As a result, their finding showed user prefers intermediate complexity over less and higher complexity to operate with. Also, minimal complexity led to users' maximum communication effectiveness. But the users' emotional responses depend on the colour contrast of the website [28] too, which was ignored in their experiment.

Seo et al. [9] proposed user emotional valence and perceived usability. It explored the relationships between users' thoughts and emotional acknowledgements. However, the weak relationships between perceived usability and emotional arousal, the aforementioned finding for arousal may not have any implications.

Lee and Kozar [10] proposed that a perceptive understanding of perceptions and purchase behaviour of consumers cannot be done without a suitable recognition of website usability. This study explains website usability constructs and measurement tools and reviews their nomological networks.

Qiuzhen et al. [15] investigated the consolidated impact of website complexity and task complexity on users' actions and visual attention. The parameters such as completion time, fixation count and fixation duration are used to distinguish task complexity (high or low) based on the load theory. They maintained track of user activities with a website, such as clicking on the screen, in addition to eye movements. Although their prior focused on finding the relationship between website complexity and user's behaviour, they did not consider individual perspectives in online shopping.

Tuch et al. [16] describe that a User's affective reaction during webpage perception is linked to Visual Complexity. Subjective feelings, behavioral expressions, and physiological responses are three levels of affective responding, and these differ as a function of Webpage Visual Complexity. In this way, a vital role in the adequate perception of Webpages is played by complexity.

An early study by Bruner and Kumar [20] revealed that the relationship between users and complex websites has many undeviating negative impressions from their three test subject sites, also mentioned in an earlier paper [22]. Conversely, positive reactions were also seen among website visitors in some aspects for visiting the complex sites, which happened indirectly. In other words, a website that has significant visual complexity can also be interesting if some particular part or information of the webpage is worthwhile for users.

Ji et al. [21] proposed a method from the user's cognitive response and behavioural information and constructed initial profiles from the 200 users dataset to create the cognitive-based model. As a result, they got positive outcomes with the customized UI/UX model compared to the traditional interface reviews.

Bonnardel et al. [23] provide the aesthetic aspects of interaction with Websites. From this perspective, identify the colours that were regarded as appealing or, on the opposite, were rejected by users and website designers. However, there were limitations. In particular, the homepages and Websites were presented to participants in a single leading colour to perform a carefully controlled experiment, and the number of participants in each of the studies was reasonably small.

Juni et al. [24] explained how to utilise the eye-tracking approach to assess consumer behaviours on web design or to discover customer interest in a certain product offered on an e-commerce website. Their work showed that it is hard to

evaluate the user experience using pupil dilation because of the size difference of a human’s pupil.

Aladwani and Palviab [25] describe empirical evaluation and verification by developing a multidimensional scale measuring user-perceived web quality. The limitations of the study cover those frequently connected with tool-building and survey programs. However, the comprehensive testing and validation gained internal validity and using several groups of subjects improved the external legality and generalizability of the instrument to a larger population.

Zhang et al. [26] proposed particular web environment aspects and sections that refer to a group of similar things. But the factors are the small representation size and the specific information-seeking task within a particular domain. Moreover, the effects of these different outcomes were not considered.

Casalo et al. [27] explain the outcome of usability satisfaction on user commitment. Still, there are gaps and limitations in existing techniques, such as the detailed way online users behaviour, privacy, security, or trust. Consequently, they proved that greater usability significantly impacts customer satisfaction.

Lin et al. [28] examined users’ emotional responses are affected by the figure-background colour contrast and visual complexity of e-commerce websites, which directly antecedent to online shopping behaviours.

Peter et al. [29] showed how they measured cognitive workload by using Nasa-TLX and dual-task methodologies in their experiment. Their primary purpose was to find the user’s mental workload for different websites. They also investigated search preference and user satisfaction using many aspects of CLT [14]. One of their major findings was online shopping websites have extraneous cognitive load because of complicated structure and presentation.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

To gather raw data from the end-user, we prepared a survey form using Google Forms which redirects to Gazerecorder [17], third-party software for giving us the heat map representation of fixation and the dwell time of every AOI (area of interest) based on the eye-tracking of the participants. We used this form for two purposes: collecting individual users’ data and the price of the chosen product. Then, we have selected 31 data set for the experiment out of 48 people’s responses and the data on the shopping experience by Gazerecorder eye-tracking software. Furthermore, all participants were well-educated and trained individuals for this study. We conducted our experiment under lab conditions to ensure its authenticity, and all our test subjects were monitored closely by ourselves.

In the first segment of our data collection, we collected some basic personal information about our volunteers who participated in the experiment. We carefully considered the device specification (screen size and webcam type) to perform the study under a similar environment for everyone. Afterwards,

TABLE I
POPULATION SAMPLING

Age Group	Characteristic		Total
	Male	Female	
18-25	7	3	10
26-33	8	6	14
34-41	4	2	6
42-50	1	0	1
In total	20	11	31

we redirect the survey-taker to the gazerecorder to track their eye movements.

The image shows a survey form with the following sections:

- Enter your PC Screen size ***: A dropdown menu with the text "Choose" and a downward arrow.
- Name ***: A text input field with the placeholder text "Your answer".
- Age ***: A text input field with the placeholder text "Your answer".
- Gender ***: Radio buttons for "Female", "Male", and "Other: _____".
- What type of Webcam you are using ? ***: Radio buttons for "External", "Internal (Laptop)", and "Other: _____".

Fig. 1. Survey Form

After reaching the gazerecorder website, the web application first scanned the person’s face through a webcam where it detected the eyeball by the movements of a redpoint. When it successfully encountered the eye-rolling gesture, it took the user to the final study page, where actual data collection occurred.

We have chosen five different e-commerce websites and set up five individual static pages by taking screenshots like Alexandre et al. [2] did in their stimuli process and displayed them in the gazerecorder’s slideshow in front of volunteers to perform the study. The products were about some random skincare cosmetics, which we showcased on those pages. Moreover, we instructed users to select one product among those products from each web page. The duration of choosing the product from a single page was 45 seconds, where we did not give any constraint about selecting any products of their wish. As a result, the participants had chosen one product

Fig. 2. Study Webpages

from each page with complete freedom under the given time. After 45 seconds, the page changes automatically and appears on the following website. In addition, the product selection process is entirely automatic, whereas each slide changes after each calibration of displaying the products. We ensured the distance between the computer screen and a participant's eye was about 75 cm (closely 2.5 feet). The total time of the experiment required for each volunteer is about 5-7 minutes. To perceive the fixations of the study, the heat map of eye-tracking data is automatically generated in the gazerecorder's system. After each study completion, we noted the experience from the participants on a scale of 1 to 5 and sought out some suggestions from them and around 60% of them rate us 5.

B. Data Processing

To understand the workflow of our data collection process, here we present Table II below. In this stage, our primary goal was to go through the raw data and observe step by step until we reached new findings of our result.

TABLE II
DATA COLLECTION WORK-FLOW

Data Collection
Data Collected from users' survey
Data Pre Processing
Classifying the Websites
Inspection and point out on the heatmaps
Counted multiple dwell's time and measured saccades from perceived data
Calculated task completion time, total fixation duration
Calculate the Standard Deviation of fixation
Data Analysis with respective methods
Method 1: Fixation
Method 2: Saccades
Method 3: Statistical Analysis

1) *Classification of Websites:* We classified some websites in our survey based on product price variation with user budget and selected five websites with three classifications low, medium, and high in Table III. Most of the products are well known popular where we surveyed, and the websites are also in the leading position in the region. A website classification is selected as low when it is most of the product prices below the customer budget that we fixed in the first place. When a website product prices are very high from the customer budget, it is classified as high. Similarly, a website classification is selected as a medium when most of the product prices are around or within the budget.

TABLE III
WEBSITE CLASSIFICATION

Name	Classification
BanglaShoppers	Low
Daraz	Medium
PriyoShop	Medium
Shajgoj	High
Paikaree	High

However, this data is not numerical. As a result, we must first transform the data into a numeric form to conduct our experiment. So we have assigned values regarding the website classification. We used scaling websites from 1 to 3 where ascending order represents low to high in Table IV. In other words, the lowest website is classified as 1, and the highest website is classified as 3, shown in the table below.

TABLE IV
WEBSITE NUMERIC CLASSIFICATION

Name	Value
BanglaShopper	1
Daraz	2
PriyoShop	2
Shajgoj	3
Paikaree	3

2) *Heatmap Inspection:* Heatmap was generated to illustrate users' eye-tracking continued AOI the study. Before we jump into our actual calculation, we need to observe heatmaps deliberately to find out users' actions. We primarily tried to find out patterns of their activity and endeavoured to seek the gap between action vs intention. In other words, heatmap analysis allows us to compare the survey data with the actual visual interest of volunteers for choosing the product. Here, heatmap generation is nothing but a tracked footprint of eye moments.

Fig. 3 illustration shows the recorded eye movement of a volunteer while selecting a product. The contrast of colours described the time difference between one to another. To put it more clearly, all footprints represent the visual interest or AOI. The more profound contrasted heatmap refers to the more time a user viewed that particular spot. We mark down the most heated spot with red circles to display the significance of AOI. This helps us understand that visual interest anticipates fixation count so that we can reach out to the actual outcome

Fig. 3. Detailed analysis of a heatmap

of the study. Furthermore, three red circles represent maximum fixations of the heatmap; hence we can say that the user concentrated carefully on those products. Although these three red spots are pretty similar from an observer point of view, we settle down to three possible outcomes or fixation counts by assuming one of these might be the chosen product. Consequently, the giant circle on the picture is the actual selected product by the test-taker. Even if we had known that from the survey data, we would also observe it from the amount of AOI it covered on the calibration picture. In addition, more heated footprints convey the larger complexity of a website [15]. That means when a website grabs more attention from a user and generates extensive impressions in the heatmap; it indicates the higher complexity of the website [16]. Therefore, a larger fixation count also refers to the larger complexity.

3) *Analyse the dataset for finding-out basic attributes:*

We classified and distinguished from relevant and irrelevant data from eye-tracking software, and named those data under different attributes. We also trimmed some data to ensure the exact time the user spent on the task. Three attributes were used in the first place to categorise the whole data which are first view, last view and dwell time of a single AOI as shown in Table V.

TABLE V
BASIC ATTRIBUTES

First view(s)	Last view(s)	1st Dwell Time(s)	Second view(s)	Last view(s)	2nd Dwell Time(s)
0.76	1.2	0.53	6.1	6.6	0.5
1.16	1.91	0.75	8.6	9.9	1.3
0.58	3.28	2.7	10.53	11.31	0.78
0.78	2.5	1.72	17.4	18.1	0.7
1.88	2.5	0.62	5.5	6	0.5
3	4.2	1.2	5.1	6.7	1.6
3.2	3.6	0.4	8.4	10	1.6
0.25	0.76	0.51	12.7	14.1	1.4

4) *Calculating specific attributes from basic attributes:*
After the data have been collected, the data have been checked and verified by matching the chosen product on both surveys outputs. There are Five significant attributes which are saccades, task completion time (TCT), Total Fixation Duration (TFD), and Total Fixation (TF) to find out for our methods. Those attributes have some pre-attributes to calculate from raw data.

- 1) Fixation
 - 1.1 Fast view of AOI
 - 1.2 Last view of AOI
- 2) Total Fixation (TF)
- 3) Average Task Completion Time (ATCT)
- 4) Total Fixation Duration (TFD)
 - 4.1 Sum of Multiple same AOI's dwell time
- 5) Saccades
 - 5.1 Last view of a Fixation
 - 5.2 First view of the next Fixation

Here, TFD + Saccades = TCT

C. *Eye tracking and task measurement*

We are going to use two different eye-tracking measurements which is Fixations and Saccades. When using eye tracking to analyze interactive systems, researchers have mostly looked at the AOI which is called fixation. Furthermore, when accomplishing a task, users visually focus on key areas of the system. On the other hand, saccadic eye movements are very distinct and task-dependent. The duration of saccades is influenced by the cognitive load [18].

1) *Fixation:* The most common sort of eye tracking event is when the eye remains focused for a long amount of time. This is known as fixation, and it can last anywhere from 200-300 milliseconds to several seconds. Fixation length is influenced by the cognitive load; the higher the load on the user, the longer the fixations [18].

2) *Saccades:* A change between two sites is another eye-tracking event. The term "saccade" refers to a voluntary movement of the eye from one fixation to the next. This is the quickest movement the human body can do, taking between 30-80 milliseconds to complete. the higher the cognitive load on the user, the longer the saccades [18].

3) *TCT:* The duration between the first view of the very first fixation and the last view of the last fixation is the TCT. TCT represent the user's total spending time to choose a product.

D. *Correlation coefficient*

Correlation analysis is one of the most extensively used and reported statistical procedures in evaluating biomedical research and scientific data. It's frequently helpful to see a connection between two independent variables. Between the calculated data of -1.0 and 1.0, a study found the features. A positive value means that an increase in one variable will rise in the other. In contrast, a negative correlation denotes an inverse relationship where one variable rises while the other decreases. On the other hand, a value of 0 correlation indicates no link between the two variables' patterns [19].

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

As we mentioned, we collected our dataset from the survey. Here we are trying to find out the reaction between users task compilation time on the webpage and website products' price variance; considering website complexity.

Now we calculate the standard deviation of saccades (SD Saccades) and fixation (SD Fixation).

TABLE VI
STANDARD DEVIATION

Website classification	SD Saccades	SD Fixation
Low	3.515	3.692
Medium	4.405	2.839
High	3.383	3.283

As we know Standard deviation represents the data as a measure of how dispersed the data is in relation to the mean. So the data presented in Table VI shows our work on data is clustered around the mean.

In methodology, there is mention of data processing and heatmap inspection. Here in the result and analysis part, different kinds of calculation will be discussed, which we apply to our dataset and find some results. Regarding those results, here we will try to explain the results.

A. Relation of users' saccades with product price

A single saccade is just a few milliseconds long events, and we have already explained the saccades in the methodology. We calculate the average of the saccades and find out that their standard deviation is 0.425, which is even less than 0.5, as shown in Table VII. That is why those websites' data are clustered.

TABLE VII
RELATION OF USERS' SACCADES

Website classification	Avg Saccades
Low	4.86
Medium	5.315
High	4.465
Standard Deviation	0.425

B. Relation of users' TF with product price

TABLE VIII
RELATION OF USERS' TF

Website classification	Total Fixation
Low	257
Medium	202.5
High	199.5

Fixation count is related to website complexity. The higher the count, the higher the complexity [15]. Table VIII shows that the relation Between website price and total fixation is inversely proportional.

TABLE IX
RELATION OF USERS' ATCT

Website classification	ATCT
Low	15.86
Medium	16.165
High	12.435

C. Relation of users' ATCT with product price

Website complexity increases if the cognitive load of user's increases. As a result, the user takes a long time to complete the task [15]. Table IX shows the inverse proportional relation with website products prices'.

D. Relation of users' FD with product price

TABLE X
RELATION OF USERS' FD

Website classification	Avg Fixation Duration
Low	11.08
Medium	7.658
High	7.74

The complexity of a website has an impact on the fixation duration it takes to maintain it. The more time passes, the complexity of the website increase [15]. Table X shows if the website price increase, then the fixation duration decrease.

E. Correlation coefficient of the product price with the dataset

We start studying with the TF and ATCT again. We calculated the correlation coefficient to see the connection between these variables and the product's price variation in Google Sheets.

TABLE XI
CORRELATION COEFFICIENT

Website Value	Total Fixation	Website value	ATCT
1	257	1	15.86
2	199	2	14.85
2	206	2	11.48
3	225	3	13.82
3	174	3	11.05
Correlation coefficient	-0.6767592578	Correlation coefficient	-0.6281633158

According to Table XI, the correlation coefficient is sequentially -0.6767 and -0.6281. It denotes a link of products' price range in a website with fixation and task compilation time. The correlation coefficient is negative; that means the strength of the relationship between these relative movements of two variables is inversely proportional.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the findings of this research, products' prices variation has an essential role in e-commerce sites. When users perform primary activities [29] like choosing a product on websites with a lower price range, task completion time

is longer on a webpage. In other words, the lower the price range, the longer it takes time to decide on a particular product. Likewise, the lower the product price, the longer users stare at that screen area to settle down for choosing a product. Fig. 4 shows the average task completion time and fixation duration in the same condition. The higher the website complexity the longer the duration of TCT and FD. It justifies our H4 hypothesis that low price products grab more attention from the user than medium and high price range products.

Fig. 4. The individual average of TCT and FD

Additionally, our study also suggests product pages have more than usual fixation and longer fixation durations on the same web page. On the other hand, saccades did not follow this pattern for the medium classification. Fig. 5 shows the SD of saccades, and average saccades follow the same rules. It illustrates a longer duration than the low and high classified websites. We know that cognitive load refers to the quantity of information that STM can process at each moment. Cognitive load theorist Sweller [14] suggests that working memory has a confined capacity. Thus, It is essential to prevent overburdening it with extraneous tasks that do not directly contribute to knowledge progress.

A. Future Work

As this is our undergraduate thesis; we narrowed down the goal due to the limited period. Hence, we did not work on any model that can help compare or find the exact issues in a website. An ideal model for e-commerce especially considering cognitive load, would do a great job. Nowadays, website developers always follow a few same rules to build a website. From that perspective, a User-interface (UI) model for an e-commerce site can effectively change the current viewpoint for anyone who is trying to build or own a new one. We will suggest some criteria to improve the website's user experience in the near future.

Here is some limitation: we can not explain a particular participant's data. To explain the exact reason for a person's AOI based on eye-tracking data was not enough. Moreover, a person's intention and action are complex, with plenty of

Fig. 5. The average and standard deviation of Saccades

inconsistent concern about what makes a person do a certain task. As a result, we estimated the visual perception of the website instead of certain AOI motivations. In the future, we want to find out the reasons behind every gaze made on the screen by a person.

Technology is evolving rapidly as we can ever imagine and what we are currently using is very different from those we used ten years ago. As a result of technological advancement, It can be assumed that using that technology in the same research will result in less erroneous and more accurate data, which will lead to nearly perfect results. Besides, we could not use the best tech to track users' eye movement or gaze due to the current pandemic. Because setting up a lab and finding participants in that situation was almost impossible to follow.

When a user browses, there are many variables that exist that directly impact cognitive user load, especially while they are looking forward to buying something online. The environment is one of the variables that influence users most. During website browsing, a buyer always tries to make the final decision; in the meantime, any surroundings can make that happen. To find out exactly what component is particularly involved with decision-making requires more time and knowledge to get an endpoint.

VI. CONCLUSION

Our purpose is to find out the relation between products' price and the cognitive load effects of the users' while they shop on an e-commerce website. A UI has many variables to up a website's complexity and products' price, one of them for an e-commerce site. People know their desired product, but whether they afford the price or not. Moreover, product choosing happens on the user's STM (Short Time Memory). That means we decide on a product faster, but the process is fragile due to decision efficiency. Especially when there are various products with the same price and a high cognitive load, users need more time to decide, which indicates high website complexity. People usually do online shopping to do it hassle-free. Therefore, we specifically work with this problem to find

an interrelation so that our findings can provide guidelines for web developers or product managers. We have organised our experiment sessions where the participants were asked to buy products from different eCommerce websites with a limited budget which was fixed. The session was conducted using a software name “Gazed Recorder”, where their eye was tracked, and then it generated a hit map for each second. The participants were also asked to fill up a google form to classify the data and verify the heat map. After the statistical analysis, we got some significant relations from our findings. We discovered a link between products’ price and cognitive load. Besides, we validated the results using two eye-tracking measurement variables. The result verified our hypotheses and found that products’ prices are inversely proportional with two variables directly related to the cognitive load. However, we hope to extend our work in the near future in this field to further our study. In this study, we are limited to many resources, and we used third party software to power up the whole experiment, which generates data manually, and we have to sort it on our own. In upcoming times, we aim to build our eye-tracking system to automatically get the desired data from the scanned outcome and plot graphs & charts to see the instant result of the observation. In addition, we have a plan to gear up our study by observing many other external responses like heart rate, expression detection and facial temperature detection while conducting the study between human and computer interaction.

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